

Studies on natrolite, a natural zeolite and its cation-exchanged and adsorbed derivatives with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, liquor NH₃ and H₂S[†]

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Abstract : These studies are based on the cation exchange and adsorption behaviour of a natrolite (Na₂O·Al₂O₃·3SiO₂·2H₂O), a natural zeolite, collected from Sinner, Nasik (Maharashtra) as a geological specimen in the powder form. Ni^{II}-natrolite and Cu^{II}-natrolite were prepared with saturated aqueous Ni^{II}-nitrate and Cu^{II}-sulphate solution respectively by continuous shaking the metal salt solution with natrolite at 60 °C for maximum interaction. A portion of this exchanged derivative was then heated over a meker burner for several days in platinum crucible. Both, the original and heated Ni^{II}-natrolite and Cu^{II}-natrolite samples were also interacted with gaseous H₂S and liquor NH₃ to study their sorption capacity and heating affects. All the derivatives prepared were analyzed by XRD and FTIR techniques.

Keywords : Natural zeolite, natrolite, cation exchange, sorption behaviour, XRD and FTIR techniques.

Introduction

Zeolites are crystalline, hydrated aluminosilicates of alkali and alkaline earth metals. Crystalline zeolites are unique adsorbent materials. Under normal conditions, the large central cavities and entire channels of zeolites are filled with water molecules forming hydration spheres around the exchangeable cations^{1,2}.

The exchangeable cations of a zeolite are loosely bonded to the tetrahedral framework and can be removed or exchanged easily by washing with a strong solution of another ion. The ion exchange and adsorption properties have been well studied³⁻⁵.

Torrie *et al.*⁶ has shown position of water molecules in natrolite framework. The water molecules and Na-cations are in the channel parallel, as couple around screw-diads. The water molecules are linked by bent hydrogen bonds to two framework oxygen. These oxygen atoms have negative charge due to the attached silicon and aluminium atoms. The positive poles of the water molecules are oriented towards this negative charge.

In continuation with our work on study of natrolites⁷, the present work deals with the synthesis of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} exchanged derivatives of natrolite and H₂S and NH₃ adsorbed derivatives of natrolite. Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} as well as H₂S and NH₃ pose environmental problems and therefore the present study may lead to a methodology for controlling these species with such natural occurring material as cation-exchangers and adsorbates.

Results and discussion

X-Ray studies : X-Ray diffraction data on Ni^{II}-natrolite, Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives are shown in the Fig. A (1-6) and Fig. B (1-6). The X-ray of Ni^{II}-natrolite, Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives are crystalline and orthorhombic (XRD data compared with 1996 JCPDS – International Center for Diffraction Data). The index of XRD data are shown in Table 1 and Table 2. The presence of aluminate tetrahedra in Ni^{II}-natrolite and Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivative framework is expected to cause an expansion in lattice. Conversely, removal of aluminium results in a contraction of unit cell.

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Fig. 1. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + stirred.

Fig. 2. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + NH₃ + stirred.

Fig. 3. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + H₂S + stirred.

Fig. 4. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + heat + stirred.

Fig. 5. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + NH₃ + heat + stirred.

Fig. 6. Natrolite (zeolite) + Ni^{II} + H₂S + heat + stirred.

Fig. A. X-Ray diffraction data on Ni-natrolite and its interacted derivatives before heating (1-3) and after heating (4-6).

Fig 1 Natrolite + Cu^{II} + stirred

Fig 2 Natrolite + Cu^{II} + NH₃ + stirred

Fig 3 Natrolite + Cu^{II} + H₂S + stirred

Fig. 4. Natrolite + Cu^{II} + heat

Fig 5 Natrolite + Cu^{II} + NH₃ + heat

Fig. 6. Natrolite + Cu^{II} + H₂S + heat

Fig. B. X Ray diffraction data on Cu natrolite and its interacted derivatives before heating (1-3) and after heating (4-6)

Table 1. X-Ray diffraction data and h, k, l value of Ni-natrolite and its interacted derivatives before heating and after heating				XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + stirred + heat			
d (Å)	h	k	l	4.5622	4	0	0
XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + stirred				4.4398	1	3	1
6.5053	2	2	0	3.9276	4	2	0
5.7820	1	1	1	3.6198	3	3	1
4.6688	0	4	0	3.3001	4	4	0
4.5723	4	0	0	2.9821	0	2	2
4.3455	3	1	1	2.8614	3	5	1
4.1685	2	4	0	2.6448	2	4	2
3.2025	1	5	1	1.8159	3	5	3
3.1259	0	2	2	1.6130	6	8	2
2.8697	3	5	1	XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + NH ₃ + stirred + heat			
2.9095	6	2	0	5.5421	1	1	1
2.8389	5	3	1	4.3546	3	1	1
2.3513	0	8	0	3.9102	4	2	0
2.1936	2	6	2	3.6337	3	3	1
1.7487	8	4	2	3.1419	5	1	1
1.7385	4	10	0	2.8722	3	5	1
1.6094	8	6	2	2.7430	5	3	1
1.5892	3	11	1	2.4392	1	7	1
XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + NH ₃ + stirred				2.0821	4	8	0
6.4764	2	2	0	1.9782	1	9	1
5.7716	1	1	1	1.8190	3	5	3
4.5496	4	0	0	1.6941	1	7	3
4.3142	1	3	1	XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + H ₂ S + stirred + heat			
4.1529	2	4	0	6.1740	2	2	0
2.8819	3	5	1	5.6112	1	1	1
2.4274	1	7	1	4.4953	0	4	0
2.2795	8	0	0	3.9484	4	2	0
1.8063	3	5	3	3.8418	3	3	1
XRD of natural natrolite + Ni + H ₂ S + stirred				3.1480	5	1	1
6.4977	2	2	0	2.9482	2	2	2
4.7356	0	4	0	2.6885	1	7	1
4.3536	3	1	1	2.0232	6	4	2
2.9045	6	2	0	1.9812	1	5	3
2.8742	3	5	1	1.8204	2	10	0
2.4220	7	1	1	1.7657	4	8	2
1.8128	3	5	3				
1.6535	0	0	4				

The diffraction data also show reduction in the number of peaks both Figs. A and B {4 to 6} which may be due to the change of space group. Residual Ni^{II}-natrolite, Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives are crystalline. So the material obtained after the heating has good

stability and good crystallinity. This stability is due to aluminium deficiency.

The X-ray data of residual derivatives show a shift of diffraction peaks to higher 2θ values as compared to Ni^{II}-natrolite, Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives,

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data and <i>h, k, l</i> value of Cu-natrolite and its interacted derivatives before heating and after heating				2.0072	6	4	2
<i>d</i> (Å)	<i>h</i>	<i>k</i>	<i>l</i>	1.8696	1	4	4
XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + stirred				1.5700	9	7	1
6.5754	1	2	0	XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + stirred + heat			
4.7226	0	3	0	6.5234	1	2	0
4.4854	3	0	1	5.4942	1	1	1
4.3826	1	0	2	4.8268	1	2	1
4.2073	1	1	2	3.4738	1	0	2
4.0517	1	3	1	3.2523	2	4	0
3.7869	0	2	2	3.1560	5	1	1
2.9278	1	1	3	2.8341	5	3	1
2.2025	3	5	2	2.6352	2	4	2
2.1267	3	4	3	2.3924	7	1	1
1.6163	4	8	0	2.0398	1	1	3
1.4322	1	3	6	1.9476	9	1	1
XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + NH ₃ + stirred				1.8229	2	10	0
6.5826	1	2	0	1.4362	7	1	4
5.7432	1	1	1	XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + NH ₃ + stirred + heat			
4.6106	2	2	1	6.5875	0	0	1
4.3860	1	0	8	5.7481	1	1	1
4.2090	1	1	2	4.8966	0	4	0
4.0625	1	3	1	4.7336	0	2	1
3.6423	4	2	0	3.9276	4	2	0
2.9084	6	2	0	3.6837	3	3	1
2.8646	3	5	1	3.3753	4	4	0
2.6642	2	4	2	3.1719	5	1	1
2.1931	2	6	2	2.8878	2	4	1
1.8579	2	8	2	2.4512	1	7	1
1.7661	9	3	0	2.3346	5	1	2
XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + H ₂ S + stirred				XRD of natural natrolite + Cu + H ₂ S + stirred + heat			
6.5886	0	2	0	6.5550	0	0	1
5.8767	1	1	1	5.6312	1	1	1
4.6126	2	2	1	4.7088	0	4	0
4.4767	0	3	0	3.9764	2	3	0
3.9703	2	3	0	3.6948	1	3	1
3.1346	5	1	1	3.1543	5	1	1
2.8818	5	2	1	2.9252	2	2	2
2.8798	3	5	1	2.6098	2	4	2
2.8342	5	3	1	2.3375	5	1	2
2.4106	7	1	1	1.8184	2	10	0
				1.7657	4	8	2
				1.4325	3	4	4

which is consistent with more siliceous framework.

FTIR studies :

The FTIR spectral data of Ni^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives with H₂S and NH₃ are reproduced in

Table 3. Ni^{II}-natrolite derivative gives bands at 3452 to 3854 and 1636 to 1698 cm⁻¹ which are mainly due to the stretching and bending vibrations of water respectively. The weak intensity band at 3801 to 3904 cm⁻¹ in H₂S

Table 3. FTIR studies of Ni-natrolite, Cu-natrolite and its interacted derivatives before heating

Assignment	Ni ^{II}	NH ₃	H ₂ S	Cu ^{II}	NH ₃	H ₂ S
	natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Ni ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Ni ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Cu ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Cu ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)
γ (OH)	3451	3426, 3427	3397	3419-3577	3409-3508	3397
δ (H-OH)	1636, 1647, 1653, 1670, 1684, 1698	1670	1636	1652	1660	1636
Pore opening	420	418	418	420	418	418
δ (T.O.)	466-480	497	459	475-487	497	459
Double ring	569-594	594-632	545, 594	609	598-633	555-598
γ sym (T.O.) internal linkage	721	697	-	722	693	-
γ sym (T.O.) external linkage	751	-	-	803	-	-
γ asym (T.O.) internal linkage	1103	-	-	959-992	988	1096
γ asym (T.O.) external linkage	988	930, 954, 988	1021	1109	-	-
δ d(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	1400	-	-	1398	-
γ (NH ₄ ⁺)	-	2361	-	-	2389	-
H ₂ S physical	-	-	1457, 1473	-	-	1399
γ (S-H)	-	-	2360	-	-	2386
γ (Si-OH) modes	3904	absent	3840, 3850, 3904	3904	absent	3854, 3850, 3982
γ (Al-OH) modes	3735	3735	3751	3758	3757	3780

interacted Ni^{II}-natrolite can be attributed to silanol bands (Si-OH bands). The band at 3735 and 3751 cm⁻¹ in natrolite is inductive of the Al-OH modes. Adsorption of H₂S on Ni^{II}-natrolite produces medium intensity bands at 1457, 1473 cm⁻¹ due to S-H linkage or sulphur containing species like sulphate, sulphite etc. and spectra of Ni^{II}-exchanged natrolite always show a peak at 559 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to Ni^{II}-O or Ni^{II}-S or something similar besides T-O bending vibration where T=(Si,Al)₄O. The band at 2362 cm⁻¹ indicates the S-H stretching vibration. Ammonia adsorbed by Ni^{II}-natrolite produces the characteristic FTIR bands at 1400 cm⁻¹ for H-N-H bending vibration. Bands at 3426, 3427 and 1636, 1670 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to N-H stretching.

The derivatives show loss of number of peaks due to heating or changed in space group. The medium intensity band at 3735 to 3770 cm⁻¹ observed in all samples. The intensity band 3801 to 3854 cm⁻¹ in samples are Si-OH modes. The H₂S interacted preheated Ni^{II}-natrolite ex-

hibits no band for physically adsorbed H₂S, only a weak band for OH stretching. NH₃ interacted derivatives show peaks at 1400 and 3451 cm⁻¹ due to H-N-H stretching vibration and the T-O stretching band at 1111 cm⁻¹.

The FTIR spectral data of Cu^{II}-natrolite and its interacted derivatives with H₂S and NH₃ are reproduced in Table 4. Cu^{II}-natrolite derivative gives bands at 3419 to 3577 and at 1652 cm⁻¹ which are mainly due to the stretching and bending vibrations of water respectively. The bands at 609 cm⁻¹ to 598 cm⁻¹ and 420 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of double ring polyhedral and T-O bending vibration in the framework. T-O bending vibration is the internal linkage frequency and is not sensitive to the topology in zeolite framework. The symmetric and asymmetric stretches of the internal linkage were also found at 722 cm⁻¹ to 693 cm⁻¹ and 1096 cm⁻¹ to 959 cm⁻¹ respectively. The weak intensity band at 3854 to 3982 cm⁻¹ in H₂S-interacted Cu^{II}-natrolite derivative can be attributed to silanol bands (Si-OH modes). The band at 3780 cm⁻¹

Table 4. FTIR studies of Ni-natrolite, Cu-natrolite and its interacted derivatives after heating

Assignment	Ni ^{II}	NH ₃	H ₂ S	Cu ^{II}	NH ₃	H ₂ S
	natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Ni ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Ni ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Cu ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)	interacted Cu ^{II} natrolite (cm ⁻¹)
γ (OH)	3494–3854	3451–3903	3459	3418, 3483, 3484	3406	3463
δ (H–OH)	1635	1636	1632	1635, 1638	1658	1634
Pore opening	408–418	439–476	480	408–418	absent	410–420
δ (T O)	456–469	488	449	476	438–475	479
Double ring	510–574	513–548	512–596	607	594	572
γ sym (T O)	623–650	615	608–644	677	675	712
internal linkage						
γ sym (T O)	-	-	-	-	-	-
external linkage						
γ asym (T O)	923, 934	937	917	988	1013	1008–1036
internal linkage						
γ asym (T O)	1114, 1156	1111	1116	1106	-	-
external linkage						
δ d(NH ₄ ⁺)	-	1400	-	-	1399	-
γ (NH ₄ ⁺)	-	2362	-	-	2385	-
H ₂ S physical	-	-	-	-	-	absent
γ (S–H)	-	-	-	-	-	absent
γ (Si–OH) modes	absent	3801, 3838, 3854	3801–3885	absent	3815	3819
γ (Al–OH) modes	absent	3711, 3735, 3750	-	absent	3711, 3735, 3758	-

in Cu^{II}-natrolite is indicative of the Al–OH modes. Adsorption of H₂S on Cu^{II}-natrolite produces a medium intensity band at 1399 cm⁻¹ due to H–S linkage and absorption band at 459 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to Cu–S linkage besides T–O bending vibrations. The band at around 2386 cm⁻¹ indicates the S–H stretching vibration.

Ammonia adsorption of Cu^{II}-natrolite produces the characteristic FTIR adsorption band at 1398 cm⁻¹ for H–N–H bending vibration. FTIR absorption band at 3409 cm⁻¹ and 1660 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to N–H stretching and N–H bending vibration respectively besides γ OH and δ OH vibrations. On treatment with ammonia, Cu^{II} ions are pulled out of the small cavities to form copper(II) ammine complex in the supercage⁸⁻¹⁰.

The derivatives show loss of number of peaks due to heating or change in space group. They show spectra of O–H bands due to loss of physically adsorbed water molecules. The medium intensity bands in the region 3711 to 3758 cm⁻¹ were observed in all samples. The band at 3815 cm⁻¹ in samples is due to Si–OH. The H₂S inte-

acted, preheated Ni^{II}-natrolite exhibits no band for physically adsorbed H₂S. NH₃ interacted derivatives show peaks 1399 and 3406 cm⁻¹ due to H–N–H stretching vibration and the T–O stretching band at 1013 cm⁻¹.

The ease with which the natrolite is able to exchange divalent metals, reveals the establishment of following equilibria :

where R is anionic aluminosilicate network.

Therefore applying suitable experimental conditions divalent metal ions could be easily removed from the aqueous medium. Natrolite can also be used for adsorption of gases like NH₃ and H₂S.

Experimental

Naturally occurring zeolite (natrolite) as a geological specimen, collected from Sinner, Nasik (Maharashtra) was powdered after cleaning, washing and grinding to very fine white particles. Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} exchanged derivative of natural zeolite was prepared by treating 20 g of this pow-

dered zeolite with 100 mL saturated aqueous solution of nickel nitrate, copper sulphate and shaken for 15 days. Reactants were warmed in an electrically operated water bath at 60 °C for maximum interaction. After 15 days, the solid natrolite was filtered and washed before air drying. A reddish-brownish Ni^{II}-natrolite and bluish Cu^{II}-natrolite exchanged derivative were obtained. One part of this sample was continuously heated over a meker burner for 10 h in platinum crucible. Dull Ni^{II}-natrolite, Cu^{II}-natrolite derivatives were obtained. Adsorbed derivatives were prepared by the procedure described in an earlier communication¹¹.

XRD data were obtained between 2θ angles of 10 to 60° with scanning rate 3° using the X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku D/max-2200). Measurements were made using 40 kv/20 mA, Cu Kα1, wavelength 1.54 Å. FTIR spectra were recorded on ABB FTLA-2000 spectrophotometer.

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